

Land-use trajectories from forest to agropastoral areas in the Chiquitano Biome, Bolivia (1985–2023)

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Abstract

The Chiquitano biome is a highly biodiverse ecosystem facing increasing pressure from agricultural and livestock expansion. In this study, we analyzed the bidirectional trajectories of land-use change between forest formations and agricultural land during the period 1985–2023, based on the Annual Land Cover and Land Use Maps from MapBiomias Bolivia (Collection 2.0). An annual multiband image was generated and land-cover classes were reclassified into two categories: “Forest formation” and “Agricultural land,” which allowed for pixel-by-pixel trajectory analysis. The study included simple and interaction linear regressions, five-year trajectories, and proportions relative to the area of origin. Results show an average annual loss of 49,158 ha of forest and an increase of 52,022 ha of agricultural land, both statistically significant. Deforestation peaked in the 2018–2023 period, with 652,031 ha converted, the highest value in the entire series. In contrast, forest recovery was limited and decreasing, dropping from 1.01% of agricultural land in 1985–1990 to only 0.23% in 2018–2023. At the five-year scale, trends were not statistically significant. These findings demonstrate that the current dynamics of land use threaten the conservation of forests in the Chiquitano biome, highlighting the urgency of policies that promote sustainable production practices.

Keywords: deforestation; land use; Chiquitano biome; trajectories

Introduction

Bolivia ranks among the ten countries with the highest forest loss over the past decade, affecting highly diverse ecosystems such as the Chiquitano region (Müller et al., 2012). The Chiquitano Biome harbors vast biodiversity of flora and fauna; it also plays a crucial role in local and regional climate regulation and supports numerous Indigenous and peasant communities (Killeen et al., 2008).

This region, in particular, has experienced an accelerated expansion of the agricultural and cattle-ranching frontier, making it one of the areas with the highest deforestation rates in Bolivia, largely driven by soybean

cultivation and the consolidation of large landholdings (Maillard et al., 2022). This dynamic of land use threatens the ecological integrity of the Chiquitano Biome, raising concerns about its biodiversity and climatic functions (Maillard et al., 2024).

Large-scale cattle ranching and mechanized agriculture, primarily for soybean production, have emerged as the predominant direct causes of deforestation (Müller et al., 2011). In addition, the growing global demand for agricultural products exacerbates pressure on tropical forests, transforming the landscape through input-intensive production methods (Henderson et al., 2021).

A detailed temporal monitoring of forest-to-agropastoral land cover changes is therefore necessary to identify the periods of highest deforestation (Killeen et al., 2007). To address this gap, the present study focuses on understanding bidirectional land-use trajectories, specifically the conversion of forest formations to agropastoral use, within the Chiquitano Biome.

Objectives

General objective

Evaluation of bidirectional land-use trajectories from forest to agropastoral areas in the Chiquitano Biome during the period 1985–2023.

Specific objectives

- Determine the total area of forest formations and agropastoral land use on an annual and five-year basis.
- Analyze the trends in land-use trajectories from forest formation to agropastoral use and from agropastoral use to forest formation.
- Establish the proportions of forest formation area and agropastoral land use for each trajectory relative to the total area of the original formation in each five-year period.

Methodology

Study area

The study area corresponds to the Chiquitano biome, one of the seven biomes defined in the MapBiomas Bolivia Collection 2.0 classification; located in the eastern part of the Department of Santa Cruz, Bolivia, and extending between 63.79° and 57.45° W longitude, and 19.57° and 14.79° S latitude. This biome lies on the Precambrian Shield and develops over an undulating plain physiography; its main forest formation is the Chiquitano Dry Forest, an ecoregion exclusive to Bolivia, recognized for hosting one of the richest dry forests in plant species worldwide

(Cuéllar et al., 2024). Historically, this region is one of the areas with the highest deforestation growth in Bolivia, experiencing a rapid expansion of the agricultural and livestock frontier in recent years (Devisscher et al., 2016).

Data

The polygon of the Chiquitano biome area used to delimit land cover and land use images was downloaded using the MapBiomas toolkit in Google Earth Engine (GEE), from MapBiomas – Collection 2.0 of the Annual Series of Land Cover and Land Use Maps of Bolivia, consulted on June 10, 2025 (Souza Jr et al., 2020).

Gain and loss detection

Using the GEE platform, a multiband image was generated for the years 1985 to 2023 (39 layers), representing land use and land cover for each year. The classification followed the official MapBiomas legend, considering two categories: Forest Formation (class 1) and Agropastoral Use (class 14). Values were reclassified to obtain a simplified binary image: Forest Formation = 1; Agropastoral Use = 2, masking all other cover types. This allowed for pixel-by-pixel evaluation of change trajectories.

Trend analysis of forest formation and agricultural use

Given the time-series nature of the data, where the value of one year is correlated with that of the previous year, simple linear regression was applied to evaluate the direction and statistical significance of the trend slope for each group: “Forest Formation” and “Agropastoral Use.” Subsequently, in order to determine whether the rate of change between “Forest Formation” and “Agropastoral Use” is significantly different, a linear regression model with interaction was employed. This model allowed for the evaluation of the difference in slope between both groups through the significance of the interaction term.

Land-use trajectories and trends

In this study, the terms transitions and trajectories are used in a complementary manner (Radwan et al., 2021). Transitions refer to discrete changes between two specific points in time (e.g., 1985 and 2023). Trajectories refer to the complete sequence a pixel may experience throughout the time series, including intermediate stages. In the five-year analyses, the term trajectory is used to indicate pixel behavior within each five-year period (not merely a comparison between two specific years). This clarification helps avoid ambiguity with discrete transitions.

Bidirectional trajectory analysis

To calculate bidirectional trajectories, each pixel was evaluated to determine whether there was a transition from forest formation to agropastoral use and vice versa over the 39 years of the series. This approach allowed for the

distinction between processes of deforestation or forest loss and regeneration or forest gain. The results were synthesized into a trajectory raster, and the areas (in hectares) of land cover, as well as those of each bidirectional trajectory per period, were calculated for the entire series.

Trajectory trend analysis

A linear regression model was used to evaluate the long-term trend of trajectory areas. The dependent variable was the area in hectares of each trajectory, and the independent variable was the starting year of each five-year period. This analysis aimed to determine whether there was an increasing or decreasing linear trend in the magnitude of the trajectories over time.

Five-year change analysis

The variation in area between consecutive five-year periods was quantified for each type of trajectory. This approach allowed for the identification of specific periods of forest formation loss or gain.

Proportion analysis

To contextualize the impact of the trajectories, the area proportions of each trajectory were calculated relative to the total area of the original formation in each five-year period. Annual total area data were consolidated at the five-year level by summing the areas of the corresponding five years. Trajectory data were then merged with the total area data of their respective original formation. Finally, the proportion was calculated by dividing the area of each trajectory by the total area of the original formation in each five-year period. Maps and statistical analyses were performed using R software version 4.5.1 (R Core Team, 2025), with the packages terra (Hijmans, 2025), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), and gspatial (Dunnington, 2025).

Figure 1. Bidirectional land-use trajectories by five-year period. A) Forest formation to agropastoral land use (forest loss). B) Agropastoral land use to forest formation (forest gain).

Results

The study area of the Chiquitano Biome covered a total of 12,510,950 ha (Figure 1). The simple linear regression analysis over the 39-year time series showed an annual coefficient of -49,158 (p-value < 2e-16), indicating an average annual loss of 49,158 ha in forest formation. For agropastoral land use, the coefficient for year was 52,022 (p-value < 2e-16), indicating a significant average annual increase of 52,022 ha. The result of the linear regression analysis with interaction yielded a coefficient of -101,181, which is statistically significant (p-value < 2e-16) (Table 1). This reflects the opposing trends between Forest Formation and Agropastoral Use during the period (Figure 2, Table S1).

Table 1. Simple linear regression coefficients: a) Trend model for forest formation and agricultural land use. b) Annual interaction model by land use. c) Trajectory model by five-year period. The year (start) corresponds to each year in the time series in (a), and to the initial year of each five-year period in (b).

Variables	Year (start)
Forest formation (ha) ^a	-49158***
Agropastoral land use(ha) ^a	52022***
Interaction ^b	-101181***
Forest f. to Agropastoral ^c	9105
Agropastoral to Forest f. ^c	634

Significance: *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05, p<0.1.

Figure 2. Annual trend of changes in forest formation and agropastoral land use (1985–2023)

The five-year trajectory analysis revealed a massive increase in agropastoral land use during the last period (2018–2023), with a change of 415,281 hectares—far exceeding the changes observed in any other five-year interval. Notable increases occurred in 1990–1995 and 1995–2000, but there was also a reduction in trajectories toward agropastoral use in 2000–2005, when the deforested area dropped to 169,460 hectares compared to 227,876 ha in the previous period (Table S2). Forest formation recovery showed substantial increases in 2005–2010 and 2010–2015, but lower values were observed in 2015–2018 and 2018–2023 (Figure 2). However, the linear regression model of five-year trajectories (Table 1), although showing a positive trend in both directions (Forest Formation to Agropastoral Use and vice versa), was not statistically significant (p -value > 0.05).

Figure 3. Five-year land-use trajectories. Forest to agropastoral use (loss) and agropastoral use to forest (gain)

The proportion of deforestation showed an upward trend during the five-year period from 1985 to 1990, with this trajectory representing only 0.21% of the total forest formation area. By the final period (2018–2023), it had increased to 1.19%. In contrast, the proportion of forest formation recovery declined notably. In the first five-year period, it accounted for 1.00% of the total agropastoral area, whereas in the last period it dropped to just 0.22% (Table S3).

Discussion

There is a clear trend of deforestation in the Chiquitano biome over the 39 years of study. The results show a significant and rapid conversion of forest to agropastoral use over the past four decades. The continuity of deforestation driven by agriculture supports the idea of insufficient forest recovery (Maillard et al., 2022, 2024).

The increase in agropastoral land use in the region during the 1990s is due to the arrival of industrial soybean farmers focused on export, livestock production, and migration to the lowlands of the Chiquitanía, driven by new employment opportunities (Killeen et al., 2007; Pinto-Ledezma & Rivero Mamani, 2014; Quintanilla, et al., n.d.). This increase in land-use change was also favored by national public policies for economic development, such as the “Eastern Lowlands” project promoted by the World Bank (The World Bank, 1998), which prioritized economic growth through agricultural expansion. These policies transformed vast forest areas into monocultures and pastures, consolidating the Chiquitano biome as a national deforestation hotspot (Jasser et al., 2021; Pacheco & Mertens, 2004).

A temporary slowdown in the rate of forest-to-agropastoral land conversion was observed during the 2000–2005 five-year period. This trend aligns with patterns seen in the Chiquitano Dry Forest ecoregions, where deforestation decreased from 256,754 ha (1996–2000) to 176,919 ha (2001–2005), representing a reduction of over 30%. During the same period, deforestation in the Cerrado also declined from 36,856 ha to 21,438 ha, a decrease of more than 40% (Müller et al., 2011; Quintanilla, et al., n.d.). This deceleration may be attributed to possible improvements in forest governance and enforcement (Quintanilla, et al., n.d.); however, it could also be explained by a combination of economic and political factors that temporarily slowed the expansion of major deforestation drivers (mechanized agriculture and intensive livestock production), possibly influenced by national political instability (2000–2005) and commodity market dynamics during that specific period (Killeen et al., 2007, 2008).

Despite these fluctuations in land-use change, there is little recovery of forest formation areas, revealing an increasingly pronounced imbalance. The conversion processes from forest formation to agropastoral use are occurring at a much higher rate than any reforestation or natural regeneration efforts, particularly during the last five-year study period (2018–2023), which could have critical consequences for the ecological integrity of the Chiquitano biome. This pattern aligns with observations highlighting the intensification of agricultural and livestock activities as primary drivers of forest formation loss in the region, especially in the Chiquitano Dry Forest, where deforestation peaks recorded between 2017 and 2020 were 63% higher (422,727 ha) compared to the 2001–2020 average (Quintanilla, et al., n.d.). A specific case is San Ignacio de Velasco, in the Chiquitanía, which

ranked first nationally in deforestation in 2017 and 2019; in those years, forest fires affected approximately 3.6 million hectares of forested areas within the Chiquitano Biome alone (de la Vega-Leinert, 2020).

Nevertheless, the trends of transformation from forest formation to agropastoral use are detected more robustly when full annual series are considered. Capturing cumulative interannual variations explains the observed statistical significance. In contrast, when data are grouped by five-year trajectories, the lower temporal resolution and data aggregation attenuate the change signal, which explains the lack of significance in regression models at that scale.

The expansion of mechanized agriculture—particularly soybean cultivation—and cattle ranching on cultivated pastures are the main drivers of deforestation (Müller et al., 2014). In the transformation from forest to agropastoral land use, cattle ranching can act as a precursor to agriculture (Kuemmerle et al., 2025), pushing the deforestation frontier and functioning as an indirect driver. This pattern of change trajectories, in which forest is first converted to grassland (Veldman & Putz, 2011) and later to agricultural land, is crucial to understanding the full dynamics of expansion over natural ecosystems (Maciel et al., 2020).

Furthermore, forest fragmentation—driven by the expansion of agropastoral land use—creates drier and more vulnerable forest edges. Being close to human ignition sources, these edges significantly increase the risk and spread of forest fires, especially considering that burning or *chaqueo* is a common and inexpensive practice to clear croplands or renew pastures in the lowlands (Maillard et al., 2020). This deforestation alters the local climate, making it drier and warmer; such drought conditions, in turn, render forests—especially their edges—more flammable, allowing fires (often initiated by the same agropastoral activities) to spread more easily and severely, destroying more forest and perpetuating the cycle (Devisscher et al., 2016).

Conclusion

The present descriptive study focuses on the dynamics of change between two land-use classes: the conversion of forest formation to agropastoral use. While this approach allows for quantifying the magnitude of transformation, future research could incorporate additional socioeconomic variables to deepen the understanding of the underlying factors driving deforestation. Despite this limitation, the results are conclusive: the Chiquitano biome is undergoing an alarming conversion of its forests to agropastoral uses, which has intensified drastically in recent years. This transformation has often been encouraged by public policies that promote the expansion of the agricultural frontier in the lowlands of Bolivia.

Deforestation not only represents the loss of a unique ecosystem such as the Chiquitano Dry Forest but also generates a degradation cycle, altering the local climate by making it drier and warmer, which in turn increases vulnerability to severe forest fires.

The limited recovery of forest cover in the face of agropastoral expansion demonstrates the unsustainability of the current model. It is urgent to redirect policies toward sustainable practices, such as agroforestry systems that integrate conservation with production, to ensure the future of this biome, which is vital for both local communities and global biodiversity.

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Supplementary Information

Table S1. Land-use changes in the Chiquitano Biome (1985–2023).

Table S2. Five-year changes in land-use trajectories.

Table S3. Proportions relative to the total area of the original formation in each five-year period.

Table S1. Land-use changes in the Chiquitano Biome (1985–2023)

Agropastoral (ha)	year	Forest formation (ha)
447524.02	1985	10804219.68
476701.65	1986	10764778.6
492035.70	1987	10761275.46
515417.03	1988	10764026.54
544188.45	1989	10742667.25
563255.62	1990	10729877.68
600075.62	1991	10701306.99
657528.88	1992	10640751.84
682433.50	1993	10625806.47
731759.17	1994	10586073.26
778531.80	1995	10557250.78
852066.80	1996	10473476.73
917089.18	1997	10399787.6
971468.16	1998	10336712.73
1002752.60	1999	10313539.69
1037352.52	2000	10286111.73
1061506.50	2001	10247480.62
1091594.91	2002	10209188.05
1135172.98	2003	10164272.61
1184197.21	2004	10109369.8
1237697.80	2005	10057957.11
1282447.51	2006	10022960.05
1321490.86	2007	9989526.728
1384620.04	2008	9919036.833
1419066.00	2009	9889390.585
1478186.68	2010	9843121.464
1528618.74	2011	9803253.229
1586522.92	2012	9759992.911
1641874.56	2013	9733786.793
1669622.39	2014	9706770.319
1704894.18	2015	9676376.013
1767785.78	2016	9610320.987
1862217.02	2017	9511947.135
1961871.33	2018	9421996.642
2058493.61	2019	9311845.144
2173742.27	2020	9242959.677
2358890.66	2021	8995305.322
2529084.66	2022	8824041.282
2733033.69	2023	8613926.541

Table S2. Five-year changes in land-use trajectories.

period	area (ha)	trajectories	area change (ha)
1985-1990	115508.97	forest to agropastoral	-
1985-1990	24885.93	agropastoral to forest	-
1990-1995	197157.42	forest to agropastoral	81648
1990-1995	24415.84	agropastoral to forest	-470
1995-2000	227876.27	forest to agropastoral	30719
1995-2000	31852.14	agropastoral to forest	7436
2000-2005	169460.18	forest a agropecuario	-58416
2000-2005	31064.27	agropastoral to forest	-788
2005-2010	205250.97	forest to agropastoral	35791
2005-2010	45714.06	agropastoral to forest	14650
2010-2015	199174.95	forest to agropastoral	-6076
2010-2015	65432.95	agropastoral to forest	19719
2015-2018	236750.15	forest to agropastoral	37575
2015-2018	40791.79	agropastoral to forest	-24641
2018-2023	652031.01	forest to agropastoral	415281
2018-2023	31721.29	agropastoral to forest	-9070

Table S3. Proportions relative to the total area of the original formation in each five-year period.

period	trajectories	area (ha)	origin	Total area (ha)	proportion
1985-1990	forest to agropastoral	115508.97	forest formation	53836968	0.21
1985-1990	agropastoral to forest	24885.93	agropastoral	2475867	1.01
1990-1995	forest to agropastoral	197157.42	forest formation	53283816	0.37
1990-1995	agropastoral to forest	24415.84	agropastoral	3235053	0.75
1995-2000	forest to agropastoral	227876.27	forest formation	52080768	0.44
1995-2000	agropastoral to forest	31852.14	agropastoral	4521909	0.70
2000-2005	forest to agropastoral	169460.18	forest formation	51016423	0.33
2000-2005	agropastoral to forest	31064.27	agropastoral	5509824	0.56
2005-2010	forest to agropastoral	205250.97	forest formation	49878871	0.41
2005-2010	agropastoral to forest	45714.06	agropastoral	6645322	0.69
2010-2015	forest to agropastoral	199174.95	forest formation	48846925	0.41
2010-2015	agropastoral to forest	65432.95	agropastoral	7904825	0.83
2015-2018	forest to agropastoral	236750.15	forest formation	28798644	0.82
2015-2018	agropastoral to forest	40791.79	agropastoral	5334897	0.76
2018-2023	forest to agropastoral	652031.01	forest formation	54410075	1.20
2018-2023	agropastoral to forest	31721.29	agropastoral	13815116	0.23